

Access Procedure to Remote Access

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Executive Summary

The **Remote Access Procedure** defines the operational framework for enabling users to access EU-SOLARIS ERIC facilities **without physical presence**, by submitting **samples or data** to be analysed or tested by qualified facility staff. This procedure is developed in alignment with the **Pilot Access Program (TA02)** approved by the EU-SOLARIS ERIC General Assembly, and supports the ERIC's statutory obligation to provide effective, merit-based access to its research infrastructures (Article 7 of the Statutes).

Through this model, **remote access** facilitates scientific collaboration and efficient use of specialized solar research infrastructure across EU-SOLARIS Member and Associated countries. It allows users to benefit from high-quality experimental results and data produced at EU-SOLARIS facilities while minimizing travel, logistical, and operational constraints.

The process involves several coordinated steps — from proposal submission and technical evaluation to sample or test rig shipment, testing, data delivery, and feedback collection — ensuring scientific rigor, transparency, and compliance with EU-SOLARIS policies on **data management, confidentiality, and safety**.

This procedure also introduces standardized documentation (Annexes I–IV) to harmonize implementation across Access Providers:

- **Annex I** – Remote Access Request Form
- **Annex II** – Access Agreement Template
- **Annex III** – Sample Shipping Guidelines
- **Annex IV** – User Feedback Form

By formalizing these processes, EU-SOLARIS ERIC strengthens its capacity to deliver **coordinated, high-quality remote services**, enhances **user experience**, and contributes to the **European Research Area's open access and sustainability objectives**.

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Table of acronyms

Acronym	Full Form
ADR	Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road
BNN	Board of National Nodes
CSP/STE	Concentrating Solar Power / Solar Thermal Energy
CST	Concentrated Solar Thermal
DMS	Document Management System
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
GA	General Assembly
GA	General Assembly
GLP	Good Laboratory Practices
IATA	International Air Transport Association
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MD	Managing Director
QA	Quality Assurance
RI	Research Infrastructure
STC	Scientific and Technical Committee

1 Purpose

This procedure establishes the operational steps, responsibilities, and quality assurance measures governing **Remote Access** to EU-SOLARIS ERIC Research Infrastructures.

It ensures that users can obtain experimental results or analyses performed on their samples, test rigs or data **without physical presence**, while guaranteeing scientific quality, safety, and data integrity.

2 Scope

This procedure applies to:

- Research facilities participating in the EU-SOLARIS ERIC Pilot Access Program as *Access Providers* under a Service-Level Agreement (SLA).
- Users submitting samples or data for analysis under *Remote Access* mode.
- All activities from proposal submission to final data delivery and reporting.

3 Definition of Remote Access

Remote Access refers to a form of user access where the physical presence of the user at the facility is not required.

Instead:

- The **user provides samples or digital data**.
- The **facility staff** perform experiments or analyses as agreed terms under the Remote Access contract.
- The **results and/or processed data** are transmitted back to the user securely.

Remote Access is distinct from **Virtual Access**, where users directly access digital datasets or software tools online.

4 Roles and Responsibilities

As described at the EU-SOLARIS ERIC's Access Policy document¹, these are the roles involved and their related responsibilities concerning remote access:

Role	Responsibility
User (Applicant)	Prepares and submits proposal, sends samples/data, and receives results.
Access Manager (AM)	Reviews test and/or evaluation feasibility, ensures safety compliance, oversees execution of tests at a Research Infrastructure of the Access Provider.
Installation Project Leader (IPL)	Is the person responsible for a project at a Research Infrastructure of the Access Provider. It is in charge of supervising the experimental activity at the installation and supporting the User in all technical, administrative and logistic needs

¹ <https://eu-solaris.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Access-Policy-28112023.pdf>

Access Committee (AC)	Evaluates and monitors facility participation and access conditions.
External User Selection Panel (EUSP)	Evaluates scientific merit and ranks proposals.
Access Coordinator (ERIC Secretariat)	Coordinates the access call, maintains records, and ensures procedural compliance.
Managing Director (MD)	Approves final access list and authorizes payments to Access Providers.

5 Access Workflow

5.1 Proposal Submission

1. The User submits an **Access Request Form** through the EU-SOLARIS ERIC portal or by email to the Central Hub (see template in Annex I).
2. The proposal must include:
 - Description of the research objective
 - Requested facility/test
 - Sample details and Material Safety Data Sheet (if applicable)
 - Expected data outputs
3. The Central Hub logs the request and forwards it to the relevant IPL for feasibility review.

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5.2 Feasibility and Scientific Evaluation

1. **Feasibility Check:**
The IPL reviews the request for:
 - Technical feasibility
 - Availability of resources
 - Safety and sample handling requirements
 - Estimated cost (based on approved unit cost)
2. **Scientific Evaluation:** The pre-approved request is forwarded to the **EUSP** for evaluation based on scientific merit and relevance.
3. **Final Decision:** The Access Committee consolidates results and proposes a final list to the **Managing Director** for approval, subject to budget availability.

5.3 Access Agreement and Sample Shipment

1. Once approved, the user and Access Provider sign an **Access Agreement** outlining:
 - Scope of work
 - IP, data, and confidentiality terms
 - Sample handling and return/disposal conditions

2. The facility provides **sample shipping instructions**, including packaging, labelling, and customs guidance.
3. Samples are logged upon receipt, and an internal **Sample ID** is assigned for traceability.

5.4 Experiment Execution

- Tests are carried out by qualified technical or scientific staff under the supervision of the IPL.
- Any deviation from the original test protocol is communicated to the user.
- All procedures follow the facility's internal safety and quality standards (ISO, GLP, etc.).

5.5 Data Processing and Delivery

- Data is processed and validated according to the facility's data management protocols.
- The following deliverables are provided to the user:
 - Raw data (if applicable)
 - Summary report or analysis
 - Metadata and calibration details (where relevant)
- Data are transmitted securely via institutional repositories or any valid secure channel as agreed on between the user and the facility.

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5.6 Sample Return or Disposal

- Samples are either returned to the user or disposed of under approved procedures.
- The user's consent for disposal is obtained in writing prior to action.

5.7 User Reporting and Feedback

- Users complete an **Access Report** and **Feedback Form** upon receiving results.
- Feedback contributes to program evaluation and quality improvement.

6 Data Management and Confidentiality

- Data generated under Remote Access are managed in accordance with the **EU-SOLARIS ERIC Data Management Policy**.
- Ownership and use rights are defined in the **Access Agreement**.
- Confidential or proprietary information is handled under strict non-disclosure terms.

7 Safety and Compliance

- All samples must be accompanied by a Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS) which will be integral part of the Access Agreement.

- The IPL ensures compliance with institutional and national safety regulations.
- In case of hazardous or sensitive materials, additional authorizations may be required.

8 Monitoring and Reporting

- Each facility maintains records of all remote accesses, including sample logs, test dates, and data delivery reports.
- The Central Hub compiles periodic summaries for the General Assembly.
- Access records are retained for at least five years for audit purposes.

9 Review and Updates

This procedure will be reviewed annually by the Access Committee and updated as necessary, particularly after the 2026 pilot phase, to reflect lessons learned and feedback from facilities and users.

Annexes

- **Annex I:** Remote Access Request Form (Template)
- **Annex II:** Access Agreement (Template)
- **Annex III:** Sample Shipping Guidelines
- **Annex IV:** User Feedback Form

Annex I: Remote Access Request Form (Template)

A. Applicant Information

Field	Description
Name and Nationality of Principal Investigator	
Name and Nationality of Team Member(s)	
Institution / Organization	
Country	
Email / Phone	
Project Title	
Funding Source (if applicable)	

B. Facility Requested

Field	Description
Name of Facility / Access Provider	
IPL (Contact)	
Requested Test / Service	
Preferred Period for Access	
Estimated Duration	

C. Scientific Description

Briefly describe the objectives and expected outcomes of the requested access (max. 300 words).

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D. Sample Information

Parameter	Description
Sample Name / ID	
Type / Material	
Quantity	
Hazard Classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Non-hazardous <input type="checkbox"/> Hazardous (attach MSDS)
Storage Conditions	
Special Handling Requirements	

E. Expected Deliverables

Raw Data Processed Data Experimental Report Other (specify)

F. Declarations

- I confirm that all provided information is accurate.
 I agree to comply with the EU-SOLARIS ERIC Access Policy, Data Management Policy, and safety requirements.

Signature (PI): _____ **Date:** _____

Annex II: Access Agreement (Template)

1. Parties

This Agreement is entered between:

(a) EU-SOLARIS ERIC Access Provider: [Name of Institution, Address, VAT, Contact]

(b) User (Principal Investigator): [Name, Institution, Address, Contact]

2. Scope of Work

The Access Provider agrees to perform the following activities on behalf of the User:

- [Brief description of experiment/test]
- [Expected results/deliverables]

3. Duration

Access Period: From [start date] to [end date].

4. Data and Results

- The Access Provider will provide raw and/or processed data and a final report.
- Data ownership and use rights follow the EU-SOLARIS ERIC Data Management Policy.
- The User shall acknowledge EU-SOLARIS ERIC and the Access Provider in any publication that uses the data or results provided.

5. Confidentiality

Both parties agree to maintain confidentiality regarding proprietary or unpublished information exchanged during this access.

6. Intellectual Property Rights

IP generated jointly will be subject to a separate agreement or shared as mutually agreed.

7. Liability and Safety

The User confirms that all samples are safe for handling under standard laboratory conditions and accompanied by safety documentation if required.

8. Termination

Either party may terminate the Agreement with written notice if obligations are not fulfilled.

Signatures

For the Access Provider	For the User
Name:	Name:
Title:	Title:
Date:	Date:
Signature:	Signature:

Annex III — Sample Shipping Guidelines

1. Pre-Shipment Coordination

- Confirm sample acceptance with the IPL before shipping.
- Include the **Remote Access ID** provided by the Central Hub on all correspondence.
- Provide **Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS)** for any hazardous materials or a legal confirmation they are not.

2. Packaging and Labelling

- Use robust, leak-proof containers and secondary containment for liquids or powders.
- Use durable containers or boxes that can be reused for shipping back after the experiments
- Label each container clearly with:
 - Sample name / internal ID
 - “FOR RESEARCH USE ONLY”
 - Sender and recipient contact details
- For hazardous or fragile samples, attach hazard symbols as per **ADR/IATA** regulations.

3. Documentation

Include inside the shipment:

- Packing list with sample IDs and quantities
- Any customs or import documentation if required

In addition, a digital copy of the Access Agreement should be sent in advance.

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4. Shipment and Tracking

- Use traceable courier services.
- Make sure to provide all delivery terms and conditions, such as delivery hours of the recipient, exact address and a contact person to the service provider.
- Send tracking number and estimated arrival date to the IPL.
- The facility will acknowledge receipt and condition of the samples within two working days.

5. Sample Return or Disposal

- Indicate in the Access Agreement whether samples should be:
 - Returned to sender
 - Disposed of under facility procedure
- Disposal will follow national waste and safety regulations.

Annex IV — User Feedback Form

A. User Information

Field	Description
Name	
Institution	
Facility Used	
Access ID	
Date(s) of Remote Access	

B. Evaluation

Please rate the following aspects from 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent):

Criterion	1	2	3	4	5
Communication and support from facility staff	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Clarity of access instructions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sample handling and logistics	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Quality of experimental results	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Timeliness of data delivery	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Overall satisfaction	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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C. Open Feedback

1. What worked well in the process?
2. What could be improved?
3. Do you plan to apply for remote access again? Yes No

Signature (optional): _____ Date: _____